

Ag/Ti-suboxides as non-PGM anode electrocatalyst for PEM water electrolysis

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Abstract

Minimization of high-cost metal electrocatalyst is necessary to achieve cost-effective green hydrogen production by proton exchange membrane (PEM) water electrolysis (WE). The large increase of the cost of Ir recently observed requires individuating alternative catalyst solutions for the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) in PEMWE. The OER is the rate determining step of the electrolysis process requiring high-cost noble metals with significantly high loading. A non-platinum group metal (non-PGM) anode catalyst based on silver and titanium suboxide was prepared and used for the oxygen evolution reaction in a PEMWE cell. By using a solid-state synthesis procedure, a silver nitrate and titanium suboxides ($\text{Ti}_n\text{O}_{2n-1}$) with Magneli phase powders were mixed and subjected thereafter to a thermal treatment at 300°C in a 50% H_2/N_2 gas stream to promote the inclusion of silver within the Ti-suboxides structure. A membrane – electrode assembly (MEA), consisting of the anode Ag/ $\text{Ti}_n\text{O}_{2n-1}$ and conventional Pt/C cathode catalysts deposited on a 212 NAFION® membrane (thickness 50 μm), was investigated to assess the performance and durability of the PGM free oxygen evolution catalyst in an acidic environment.

A promising performance, of $0.6 \text{ A}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ at 2 V/cell at 80°C , and an excellent stability (degradation rate $< 14 \mu\text{V/h}$ during a 1000 h test) were achieved for the electrolysis cell based on a cost-effective metal anode electrocatalyst.

Keywords: Hydrogen production; water electrolysis; Proton exchange membrane; oxygen evolution reaction; non-PGM catalysts.

1. Introduction

The extensive use of fossil fuels is associated to severe environmental risks, such as the depletion of natural resources, the generation of waste, the emission of pollutant gasses with a negative effect on climate changes. In this context, the use of renewable energy sources, in particular those related to the sustainable production of electric energy is growing rapidly [1-4]. However, solar, wind and hydroelectric energy, which are among the most common renewable power sources, are characterized by a discontinuous availability, due to weather changes and seasonal features [5]. Therefore, it is essential to find efficient and cost-effective processes allowing to store and convert renewable electricity by using the energy surplus when it is required. This need requires developing innovative energy conversion and storage systems, such as the production of hydrogen through water electrolysis, the conversion of hydrogen in electric energy by means fuel cells and the manufacture of advanced batteries for the energy storage [5-7]. Nowadays, hydrogen is the main rising clean and green energy carrier produced due to its high energy density and wide application perspectives. Green hydrogen can be produced by water splitting through electrolysis according to four main different technologies: polymer electrolyte membrane-based [8-14], liquid electrolyte alkaline-based [8, 15, 16], anion exchange membrane-based [8, 17-19] and the solid oxide-based at high temperatures ($700\text{-}800^\circ\text{C}$) [8]. With respect to the other electrolysis technologies, proton

exchange membrane devices are featured by high performance also at low temperature, long durability and great capability to handle duty cycles, good dynamic behaviour and, specially, ability to work at high current densities with high energy efficiency [8-10, 20]. Nevertheless, the most important property of these systems is the ability of producing hydrogen at high pressures with high purity [4]. This is a considerable advantage, as this involves a decrease of the post-compression energy consumption [21]. Thus, this technology can lead to cost savings by working at high current density if a lower use of high-cost metal catalysts is implemented [9, 22-29].

Currently, only noble metals, PGM-based, such as Ir and Ru, are known as efficient and stable catalysts for the OER in acidic media [30]. However, these elements are extremely rare in nature and this may limit the large scale deployment of hydrogen production by PEM water electrolysis. Another important aspect to mention is the dramatic increase of the cost of these metals in the last years [31]. The iridium cost was stable up to the year 2020, after that it has grown from 45 to 150 €/g today [31]. A similar situation has been observed for the ruthenium cost which has increased from 8-9 to 19 €/g today [31]. The high risk associated with the availability and high cost of these metals requires to address specific efforts to the development of cost-effective catalysts for the oxygen evolution reaction that is more demanding in terms of electrocatalyst mass loading being the rate determining step of the overall process.

In recent years, various studies have been focused on the development of electrocatalysts based on non-PGM and other cost-effective electrocatalysts for oxygen evolution [32-37].

However, to the best of our knowledge, no efficient cost-effective catalysts formulation has been yet valuated in terms of activity and stability in single cell [38, 39]. Some literature reports have dealt with single cell studies of non-PGM cathode, e.g. FeS₂ [40] and MoS₂ nanosheets in-situ grown onto the carbon fiber paper [36] as cost-effective cathode catalysts for the hydrogen evolution

reaction in a PEM electrolysis single cell. In the latter case, at 2 A cm^{-2} a cell voltage of 2.25 V was obtained with $3 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ IrRuOx anode catalyst coated on a Nafion 115 membrane-based MEA [36]. Regarding the anode, essentially only Co-based catalysts as PGM free materials have been investigated [41] showing limited current density (420 mA cm^{-2} at 2 V).

The choice of PGM-free catalysts formulation that excludes Ir, Ru or Pt for the oxygen evolution in PEMWE is limited by the harsh operating environment due to the low pH and high electrochemical potential.

Recently, titanium oxide and titanium suboxides ($\text{Ti}_n\text{O}_{2n-1}$, $4 \leq n \leq 10$), also known as Magnéli phases, have been studied as metal oxide supports for anode catalysts in PEMWE. These are not affected by corrosion as it occurs with carbon-based materials for the OER reactions [42, 43]. In more detail, $\text{Ti}_n\text{O}_{2n-1}$, is characterized by a crystalline structure obtained by a thermal reduction of TiO_2 with hydrogen, the resulting substoichiometric oxide shows a good electron conductivity due to the oxygen vacancies in the matrix [44].

Another important aspect in PEM electrolysis is regarding the possibility of achieving low ohmic loss by using relatively low membrane thickness ($\leq 50 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$). This has an important impact on the electrochemical process due to the reduced resistance to ionic transport at specific operating temperatures ($\leq 90 \text{ }^\circ \text{C}$). These effects could in part compensate for the lower electrocatalytic activity of non-PGM catalysts compared to Ir, Ru or Pt metal catalysts to achieve similar performance of conventional PEM electrolyzers, at moderate operating pressures.

The aim of this work is to identify a cost-effective catalyst formulation that does not include Ir, Ru or Pt with promising characteristic in terms of activity and stability for the oxygen evolution in PEMWE. Validation of such novel anode material in a practical single cell device can allow getting insights into possible large-scale applications.

Accordingly, a silver and titanium suboxides-based anode catalyst was prepared and assessed for the evaluation of oxygen evolution reaction in a PEM electrolysis device.

In the literature, the OER activity of silver has been studied only in half-cells based on liquid electrolytes. For example, in a study from Yan et al. [45], Ag-doped Co_3O_4 supported on FTO has demonstrated a promising OER activity in acidic media with an electrochemical potential of 1.91 V vs. RHE at the current density of 10 mA cm^{-2} and a high stability at a constant overpotential of 370 mV for 10 h.

Gao et al. [39] discussed the Pourbaix diagram of silver in combination with electrolysis studies. This is a powerful tool for exploring the thermodynamic stability of the electrocatalysts under specific reaction conditions (e.g., pH and potential). This diagram can be used as a reference to assess the thermodynamic stability of metal or metal oxides in acidic OER conditions, typically at pH 0–3 and at a potential of 1.5–2.0 V versus RHE. They found that Ag forms stable oxides in acidic OER conditions.

A. Jain et al. [46] reported a study on Stable Two-Dimensional Materials for ORR and OER, demonstrating that Ag-based oxides and hydroxides are stable conductors under OER conditions in acid environment.

Our work provides a further step towards the application of Ag-based catalyst in electrolysis. Here we show that cost-effective silver-based catalysts can achieve practical electrolysis performances comparable or even better than those of conventional liquid alkaline electrolysis with good stability for 1000 h at least, under steady state conditions. We have also identified some issues that require specific ameliorations especially in terms of morphology and some weakness related to the stability towards cycled operation.

In more detail, in this paper, a membrane – electrode assembly (MEA), composed by an $\text{Ag}/\text{Ti}_n\text{O}_{2n-1}$ anode, a Pt/C cathode catalysts and a 212 NAFION® membrane (thickness 50 μm), was investigated in terms of performance and durability. A durability test of 1000 h was carried out and the variation of catalyst properties was investigated by post-operation physico-chemical analysis of structure morphology and surface properties.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

For the oxygen evolution reaction (OER), an Ag-titanium suboxides catalyst was synthesized by a solid-state procedure. A silver nitrate precursor was supplied by Carlo Erba. Titanium suboxides powder ($\text{Ti}_n\text{O}_{2n-1}$) with Magneli phase, was prepared from a commercial titanium (IV) chloride solution (TiCl_4 , Aldrich) by complexation of Ti ions and successive decomposition of the complex to form an amorphous oxide [42]; this was subsequently reduced by a thermal treatment ($1050\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) with diluted hydrogen (Fig. S1) [47]. AgNO_3 and $\text{Ti}_n\text{O}_{2n-1}$ were mechanically mixed in the molar ratio of 30:70 in a porcelain mortar and ball milled in a planetary mill for 12 h/300 rpm to obtain an Ag/Ti-suboxides mixture. This Ag/Ti-suboxides-based catalyst was subjected to a thermal treatment at $300^\circ\text{C}/1\text{h}$ in a tubular quartz reactor fed with a 50% H_2/N_2 gas stream to promote the inclusion of silver within the Ti-suboxides (Fig. S2).

A perfluorosulfonated ion-exchange membrane, Nafion[®] 212, provided by Ion Power, with a thickness of 50 μm and an equivalent weight (EW) of 1100 g/eq was employed as membrane separator for the electrodes in the PEM electrolysis cell. The electrode for the anodic compartment was manufactured using a titanium porous transport layer (PTL, 300 μm thick, characterized by about 70 % porosity) onto which an ink consisting of 80 % Ag/ $\text{Ti}_n\text{O}_{2n-1}$ catalyst and 20 % Nafion[®] ionomer dispersed in isopropanol was sprayed (Fig. S3). The cathodic section was composed by a carbon gas diffusion layer (GDL ELAT from E-TEK) onto which an ink made of 40% Pt/C (Alfa Aesar) and 33% Nafion[®] ionomer was deposited by using the doctor blade coating method. MEAs components (cathode, membrane and anode electrode) were hot pressed at $130\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 2 kN both for 2 minutes. The MEA, having 5 cm^2 electrode area, was mounted in a cell housing equipped with a titanium plate on the anodic side and a graphite plate on the cathodic side. The catalyst loadings for the anode and cathode were 12 and 1.25 mg/cm^2 , respectively.

2.2 Chemical-physical characterizations

Physico-chemical and morphological properties of the catalysts were studied by X – ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and X- ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). A Bruker D2 PHASER desktop diffractometer, operating at 40 kV and 20 mA, was used for investigating the structural properties of the catalysts. The measurements were conducted in a Bragg-Brentano geometry with a scan rate of $0.5^\circ 2\theta \text{ min}^{-1}$. The diffraction patterns were analysed through the Joint Committee on Powder Diffraction Standards (JCPDS). SEM analyses were carried out by means of a FEI S – FEG XL30 microscope coupled with an energy dispersive X-ray spectrometer (EDX), operating at 25 kV before and after the steady-state operation (1000 h) and voltage cycles (24 h) tests. The anode surface composition was studied by using a Physical Electronics (PHI) 5800 – 01 spectrometer before and after durability and cycle tests as well.

2.3 Electrochemical investigations

The performance and stability of the PEM electrolysis cell were investigated by means of electrochemical studies at 80°C and under ambient pressure conditions. Deionized water (Milli – Q integral Millipore) with a resistivity of $18.2 \text{ m}\Omega \cdot \text{cm}$, was fed to the anodic compartment with a flow rate of $1 \text{ ml} \cdot \text{min}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$ and was left to recirculate at the same temperature of the cell. Galvanostatic polarization curves and durability tests (cell potential vs. cell current and cell potential vs time, respectively) were obtained by using a TDK Genesys™ 25400 – MD – 3P400 power supplier. A cut off of 2.5 V was selected.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) analyses were performed at 1.5 V and 1.8 V by varying the frequency from 100 kHz to 100 mHz in single sine mode by using an Autolab PGSTAT 302 Potentiostat/Galvanostat, equipped with a Metrohm 20 A booster and a frequency response analyser (FRA). The amplitude of the sinusoidal excitation signal was 0.01 V r.m.s. 50 log scale

frequencies were swiped in descending order. The series resistance was determined from the high frequency intercept on the real axis in the Nyquist plot.

3. Results and discussion

The synthesis of the Ag/Ti-suboxides catalyst includes a first step related to the formation of titanium suboxides. This involves formation of an amorphous oxide phase with a subsequent reduction at 1050°C. Fig. S1 (Supplementary Information) shows the SEM - EDX analyses of the obtained Ti-suboxides. No relevant amounts of impurities that may derive from the precursors are detected. Structural and physico-chemical characterizations (see below) have confirmed the presence of the Ti_nO_{2n-1} formulation with Magneli phase. In particular, the observed Ti/O at. ratio 0.82 (Fig. S1) is in good agreement with the general sub-oxide formulation Ti_nO_{2-n} that is indicative of the presence of specific oxygen vacancies. The achievement of a proper purity for the TiOx support with a Magneli phase structure containing a proper amount of oxygen vacancies represents one of the main challenge in the preparation of this anode catalyst.

In the second step of catalyst preparation, the Ag precursor is mechanically mixed with Ti-suboxides. Thereafter the catalyst powder is subjected to a thermal treatment at 300 °C for 1 h with a 50% H₂/N₂ gas stream to promote the inclusion of silver within the Ti-suboxides structure. Fig. S2 shows a comparison of XRD patterns from different Ti phases, before and after the thermal treatment with Ag.

An XRD pattern of the Ag/Ti-suboxides anode catalyst subjected to the thermal treatment at 300°C/1h with H₂ and N₂ (50:50%) is reported in Fig. 1. After a preliminary investigation of the thermal treatment up to 500 °C, a reduction treatment at 300 °C was selected to favour the inclusion of silver with the Ti-suboxides, while avoiding excessive sintering of catalyst particles. The AgNO₃ precursor was reduced to Ag nanoparticles during such treatment. The main diffraction peaks at 38°

and 44° 2θ were assigned to the 111 and 200 reflections of metallic Ag with face-centered cubic crystallographic structure (JCPDS: 04-0783). A crystallite size of 46 nm was determined from the Debye-Scherrer equation. The typical peaks of Ti_nO_{2n-1} (with n varying from 4 to 10) Magneli phase structure, after the thermal treatment, are evident especially for the phases characterised by $n = 4, 5$ and 6. The inset shows the SEM image of the catalyst, a good dispersion of Ag on the Ti-suboxides is observed. SEM-EDX analysis showed no relevant impurities (Fig. S1). The composition after the reduction treatment was of 30:70 at. % Ag/Ti-suboxides.

Fig. 1 X-ray diffraction patterns of the Ag/Ti-suboxides anode catalyst (JCPDS cards no. 04-0783 (Ag), 1527759 (Ti_4O_7), 1520779 (Ti_5O_9), 1008201 (Ti_6O_{11}); inset: SEM image of the Ag/Ti-suboxides catalyst.

Regarding the electrochemical characterization, polarization curves (cell potential as a function of current density) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) were carried out (Fig. 2a-b). The Ag/Ti-suboxides catalyst (30-70 at %) thermally reduced in a H_2-N_2 stream showed an ohmic loss corrected (IR-free) single cell performance of $0.6 A cm^{-2}$ at 2 V and $2 A cm^{-2}$ at 2.15 V (Fig. 2a). The raw performance at $0.6 A cm^{-2}$ was 2.1 V/cell. This corresponded to a voltage efficiency of 70%. The

cell voltage at 0.6 A cm^{-2} is assumed as key performance indicator of the voltage efficiency since this is a typical operating current density of advanced liquid alkaline electrolyzers that do not make use of PGM metals.

The electrochemical characterization of a single cell based on IrO_2 as anode and Pt/C as cathode is reported in Fig. 2c, 2d. The single cell voltage of the MEA with Ag/Ti -suboxides anode catalyst was higher than a conventional PEMWE based on a precious Ir-based anode (Fig. 2a, 2b vs. Fig. 2c, 2d). The total anode catalyst loading was significantly higher in this work compared to conventional PEM electrolyser (12 vs conventional 2-3 mg cm^{-2} for the benchmark IrOx catalyst) [48, 49]. However, the silver loading in the Ag/Ti -suboxides anode catalyst (3.3 mg cm^{-2}) was comparable to the standard Ir loading in conventional PEMWE anodes.

Fig. 2 Polarisation curves (a) and AC-impedance spectra (inset: high magnification) (b) at 1.8 V and 2 V at 80 °C for the MEA with Ag/Ti-suboxides anode catalyst; Polarisation curves (c) and AC-impedance spectra (d) at 1.5 V at 80 °C for the MEA with IrO₂ anode catalyst.

The behaviour of the electrolysis cell based on the Ag/Ti-suboxides anode catalyst was studied by impedance spectroscopy at 80 °C and two different cell voltage values, 1.8 and 2 V, representative of activation and ohmic-mass transfer control regions, respectively (Fig. 2b). Similar series resistance values (intercept of high frequency on the real axis) were recorded by Nyquist plots, 145 mΩ cm², for the two different cell voltages (Fig. 2b).

The membrane usually gives the main contribution to the series resistance, whereas the polarization resistance (R_p) is mainly due to charge and mass transfer. The R_p for the two voltage values, 1.8 and 2 V, decreased significantly as the cell voltage value increased (Fig. 2b). The R_p values at 1.8 V and 2 V were 1.48 Ω cm² and 0.210 Ω cm², respectively. R_p was estimated from the difference of the low and high frequency intercept of the Nyquist plot on the real axis. The strong decrease of polarization resistance passing from 1.8 to 2 V (Fig. 2b) was largely indicative of an activation control associated to the oxygen evolution at the Ag/Ti-suboxides catalyst. Whereas the Pt/C cathode catalyst being associated to a fast electrochemical process had much lower or negligible impact on the impedance plot [50]

Fig. 3 Steady-state durability test at 0.6 A cm^{-2} and $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ of the MEA with Ag/Ti-suboxides anode catalyst (a); Polarization (b) and AC-impedance spectra at 1.8 V (c) and 2 V (d) at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ of the MEA with the Ag/Ti-suboxides anode catalyst at BoL and after the steady-state durability test

The stability of the Ag/Ti-suboxides anode catalyst was studied by a steady-state durability test of 1000 h at ambient pressure and 80°C (Fig. 3). The durability test, performed at $0.6 \text{ A}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, is reported in Fig. 3a. This time-study appeared appropriate to get some first insights about the behaviour of the novel anode electro-catalyst used in PEM water electrolysis in order to identify possible causes of degradation. After a rapid slight increase of the cell voltage in the first hours of operation, a stable cell potential of about 2.1 was observed. It is reasonable to consider that sub-oxides tend to revert to stoichiometric oxides at the potentials relevant for the OER, leading to a reduced conductivity. Such increase of resistivity may have caused the observed increase of cell voltage of a few tens of millivolts, in the first hours of operation of the steady-state durability test.

An interruption of the test after 350 h, due to plant maintenance issues, showed some small additional losses without however affecting much the voltage efficiency. The cell voltage was much higher compared to conventional Ir-based MEAs [9]. For the Ag/Ti-suboxides (30:70) based MEA an overall degradation rate of about 14 $\mu\text{V}/\text{h}$ was observed by removing the first 24 h conditioning period, that correspond to $< 0.7 \%/1000 \text{ h}$.

The MEA based on Ag/Ti-suboxides anode catalyst was subjected to polarization and impedance spectroscopy studies before and after the 1000 h steady-state test (Fig. 3b-d). The comparison of the polarization curves carried out before and after the durability test is reported in Fig. 3b. A better performance (lower cell voltage) for the polarization curve after the durability test is indeed observed. Such evidence indicates that the increase of the cell voltage during the overall durability test (Fig. 3a) was essentially associated to the load cycle at 350 h. The improvement recorded in the polarization curve (Fig. 3b) was probably due to an enhancement of the catalytic activity and to better interfacial characteristics occurring in the activation and ohmic-mass transfer-controlled regions after the durability test. The increase of performance (i.e. the decrease of cell voltage at the same current density) in the polarization curve (Fig. 3b) was moderate in the activation region (35 mV at 0.6 A cm^{-2}) and larger at high current density (95 mV at 1.8 A cm^{-2}).

AC-impedance analysis revealed that, after the durability test, a lower R_s was recorded in the impedance spectra at both 1.8 V and 2 V (Fig. 3c, 3d). This was probably due to an in situ purification of the membrane or it was slight thinning of the membrane with time. The R_s decreased by $45 \text{ m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$, for the two different cell voltages 1.8 and 2 V (from about 0.15 to $0.1 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$).

A decrease of polarization resistance at low frequency was evident in the impedance spectra at 1.8 V after the durability test (Fig. 3c) and indicated better interfacial characteristics, between the

catalysts and membrane. The R_p decreased from 1.48 to $0.9 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ at 1.8 V after the 1000 h steady-state durability test (Fig. 3c).

The larger impact on the decrease of the cell voltage of high current density was in part due to the decrease of the series resistance. Anyhow, these results show good catalyst stability properties.

Fig. 4 Voltage cycle test (a) at 1 - 1.8 V and 80 °C and steady-state durability test (b) of the MEA with Ag/Ti-suboxides anode catalyst.

To understand the effect of load cycles, a voltage cycle test was carried out. The same MEA was subjected to a voltage cycle test at 1 – 1.8 V at a low frequency (0.02 Hz) in order to evaluate the single cell behaviour under stress conditions; the duration of this specific voltage cycling was 24 h at 80°C (Fig. 4a). Some current decay during the first hours was observed. The current value recorded at the beginning of the cycle test corresponded to that observed in the polarization curve after the steady-state durability test (Fig. 3a). The initial value was about 70 mA cm⁻² at 1.8 V. The current decay led to a current of 20 mA cm⁻² after 24 h test. This loss was probably due to the catalyst degradation or change on the anode catalyst oxidation state during this stress test.

Thereafter a steady-state durability test at 0.6 A·cm⁻² and 80 °C was carried out to evaluate the effect of the voltage cycle test on the cell stability. A comparison on the two different steady state tests, before and after cycle test, is reported in fig. 4b. An irreversible loss of performance was evident but no relevant impact was observed on the steady state degradation rate. A decay of 50 mV was recorded after the 40 h duty cycle test.

Fig. 5 Polarisation curves at 80 °C for the MEA with the Ag/Ti-suboxides anode catalyst before and after stability and cycle tests.

Fig. 5 shows a comparison of the polarization curves for the BoL MEA and the MEA subjected to steady-state operation (1000 h) and to the voltage cycles test (24 h). An increase of the cell voltage at very low current was observed after the voltage cycle test procedure. The cycle test also caused an increase of cell voltage in the current density region up to 0.5 A cm^{-2} revealing some additional activation losses compared to the MEA not subjected to duty cycles.

Ex-situ post-operation analyses were carried out on the BoL MEA and used MEA, in order to understand the catalyst degradation or any change on the anode catalyst oxidation state that could have occurred during the voltage cycle test. The XRD patterns of the Ag/Ti-suboxides anode catalyst and membrane of the used MEA are reported in Fig. 6. There was a lower evidence of metallic Ag in the used anode, scraped from the MEA, essentially the Ti-suboxides were present. No change in crystallite size for Ti_4O_7 , Ti_5O_9 and Ti_6O_{11} based-Ti-suboxides before and after test was observed (Figs. 1 and 6a). The XRD pattern of the used membrane is reported in the Fig. 6b. The peaks of the metallic Ag were evidently present in the membrane pattern. This means that the metallic Ag migrated inside the membrane or Ag particles stucked better to the membrane than the Ti-suboxide support during operation. The decrease of polarization resistance, observed in Fig. 3b, was probably associated to the better interface between the Ag particles and the solid polymer electrolyte. However, activation losses increased during the duty cycles (Fig. 5). One could speculate about the fact that Ag is mainly responsible of the catalytic activity whereas the Ti-suboxides provide mainly support to the electronic percolation. The presence of Ag into membrane indicates a stronger interaction to the solid polymer electrolyte than the electronic conductivity support.

As well known, the XRD analysis gives information about the bulk structure where no particular change of the Ag based-anode catalyst oxidation state was observed. A reduction of crystallite size for the metallic Ag was observed after the durability test, from 46 nm at BoL to 25.3 nm at the end of life (EoL) (Figs 1 and 6b).

Fig. 6 X-ray diffraction patterns of a) Ag/Ti-suboxides catalyst scraped from the MEA and b) Nafion N212 membrane after the stability and cycle test

A morphology investigation of the Ag/Ti-suboxides anode, scraped from a fresh MEA, and the MEA after the voltage cycling test are shown in Fig. 7. The SEM analysis (Fig. 7a-7c) showed for the Ag/Ti-suboxides-based fresh anode the occurrence of mixture of nanosized irregularly shaped and faceted particle agglomerates formed of fine particles ($\leq 10 \mu\text{m}$), associated to the Ti-suboxides. The Ag particles were more evident in Fig. 7b and 7c, at higher magnifications with agglomerates smaller than a few hundred micrometres. In the BoL sample, the presence of the ionomer was evident, whereas in the used sample the ionomer was less observed (Fig. 7a-7c vs. Fig. 7d-7f). A decrease of the atomic ratio F/Ti was recorded by SEM-EDX. No significant change in morphology with the

durability test (Fig. 7d-7f) was observed, just a sintering of metallic Ag in the used sample compared to the fresh samples in contrast the observation by X-ray diffraction (Fig. 6b).

Fig. 7 SEM for Ag/Ti-suboxides anode catalyst before (a, b, c) and after (d, e, f) durability and duty cycles

Fig. 8 XPS for Ag/Ti-suboxides anode catalyst before and after durability and duty cycles

High resolution XPS analyses were carried out on the anodic surface of a fresh MEA and used MEA subjected to durability and duty cycles; Ag3d and Ti2p photoelectron lines were selected for the assessment of Ag and Ti oxidation states (Fig. 8a, 8b). By comparing the B.E. of Ag3d peaks, a shift to lower B.E. in the used sample was evident (Fig. 8a) and this was related to an oxidation of the Ag⁰ to Ag⁺ for the used anode-based MEA [51]. The B.E. shifted from 367.97 eV in the fresh catalyst to 367.18 eV in the used catalyst. It is worth mentioning that in the case of silver, formation of oxidised Ag from metallic Ag is usually accompanied by a negative shift of the B.E. contrary to what occurs with most of the metals [52].

The high resolution spectra of Ti2p before and after the durability and duty cycles test are reported in Fig. 8b. In this case a shift at higher B.E. was observed for the used sample indicating an oxidation of the Ti surface. The shift indicated a partial modification of sub-stoichiometric Ti-suboxides species on the anode surface that produced a higher oxidised phase. The reoxidation of Ti suboxides to form TiO₂ on the surface under electrolysis conditions may have an impact on both series and polarisation resistance being these part of a catalyst-ionomer composite network that extends the reaction zone from the catalyst-membrane interface to the catalytic layer. However, such surface re-oxidation of titanium did not produce any relevant impact on either series or polarisation resistance values after the steady state durability test (Fig. 3). Moreover, the slope of the polarisation curve at high current density in Fig. 5, after the cycling test, was even smaller that at the beginning of test.

To summarise, XPS analysis has clearly indicated an oxidation of the Ti-suboxides on the surface. However, this does not cause any dramatic performance loss during 1000 h steady state operation under electrolysis conditions, or increase of series and polarisation resistance or increase of the slope of polarisation curves at high current density. Thus, it is speculated that some breaks in the TiO₂ oxide surface layers may occur at high potentials allowing an electronic percolation eventually by a tunnelling effect [53-58] as it occurs with Ti bipolar plates in conventional PEM electrolysis

stacks. This would suggest that the growth of the TiO₂ oxide layer remains confined to the surface in the present Ti sub-oxides and electronic percolation possibly occurs through alternative mechanisms. Our electrochemical and physicochemical results seem to confirm such aspects. In particular, the surface oxidation of the sub-oxides detected by XPS was not observed in the XRD analysis of the anode support after the durability study. This indicates that the bulk characteristics are not significantly changed.

Accordingly to Gasteiger et al., [59], titanium suboxides are a promising support option with higher intrinsic conductivity compared to antimony tin oxide (ATO) [42, 60], but further research is required to show if this high conductivity can be maintained during prolonged electrolyser operation. The present work provides evidence that after some potential losses in the first operating hours, the system stabilizes possibly due to the contribution of a tunnelling effect on the electronic percolation. The oxidation of Ti-suboxide may be instead responsible for the lower interaction of Ag with the catalyst support after operation causing an increase in activation losses.

This first assessment of a novel Ag/Ti_nO_{2n-1} oxygen evolution catalysts indicates that, beside the relatively lower performance compared to iridium oxide, other specific issues are individuated. These especially regard a surface re-oxidation of the Ti-suboxide support, a poor interaction between the Ag phase and Ti-suboxide after cycling whereas a good interaction with the ionomer is observed. Moreover, an irreversible loss of performance was clearly observed during the voltage cycling between 1 and 1.8 V. Gao et al. [39] observed that Ag can form stable oxides in acidic OER conditions whereas A. Jain et al. [46] noticed that the formed Ag-based oxides are stable conductors under OER conditions in acid environment. However, according to the Pourbaix diagram, silver may corrode in a substantial potential region in the lower potential range of the OER and below which may have bearings on degradation during on-off cycles in intermittent water electrolysis operation. Such evidences may explain the high stability under steady-state operation compared to the cycling

mode and reveal some limitations of this catalytic system for specific operating conditions. All these grounds are relevant for a successive optimisation study.

4. Conclusions

Considering the recent dramatic increase in the Ir cost, this work aims at finding an anodic formulation alternative to iridium-based anode catalysts. The large increase of Ir cost appears mainly related to the insufficient reserves to manage all potential applications including PEM electrolysis fed by renewable power sources. This is a well consolidated technology to produce green hydrogen. The limited Ir reserves could thus limit PEM electrolysis in contributing significantly to the installation of the required electrolysis plans, in the order of tens of GW, as planned in several countries. The risks associated to the high cost and availability of iridium clearly indicate the need to explore alternative solutions.

In this regard, the present work provides an electrochemical single cell assessment of a non-PGM anode catalyst for PEM electrolysis applications. A solid-state procedure was used to obtain Ag/Ti-suboxides, from silver nitrate and titanium suboxides with Magneli phase. The thermal reduction process promoted the inclusion of silver within the Ti-suboxides. The MEA, consisting of Ag/Ti-suboxides anode, Pt/C cathode catalysts and 212 NAFION® membrane, showed promising performance and durability characteristics in comparison to analogues alkaline systems based on PGM-free catalysts. At 80°C, performances, of 0.6 A·cm⁻² at 2 V and 2 A·cm⁻² at 2.2 V IR-free were observed together with an elevated stability during steady-state operation.

Such electrochemical results clearly show a lower performance for the novel Ag/TiOx formulation compared to a well optimised IrOx-based anode catalyst in a PEM electrolysis cell. However, the performance achieved with the Ag/TiOx anode appears already competitive to liquid alkaline electrolysis technologies.

Some degradation was observed upon application of duty cycles. This had a negative impact on the catalyst behaviour causing some activation losses.

Post operation analysis showed some catalyst agglomeration and migration of silver onto the membrane which was indicative of lower interaction with the TiO_x phase. An increase of the oxidation states for Ag and Ti was also observed. However, such modifications did not produce relevant performance losses. In general, there is still a good possibility of improving catalyst properties in terms of dispersion, particle size and interface with the solid polymer electrolyte in a PEM electrolysis cell.

Thus, the developed Ag/TiO_x catalyst effectively requires some improvements before becoming a satisfactory replacement for the IrO_x benchmark. Our work was essentially addressed to provide a basis for an alternative catalyst formulation that could undergo to successive amelioration. As mentioned above, the required improvements regard the achievement of a mesoporous catalyst morphology, a decrease of the particle size, a better inclusion of Ag in the Ti suboxide structure etc.

A specific challenge regards the performance decrease after the load-cycling test due to the migration of metallic Ag inside the membrane. It appears that some Ag nanoparticles better adhere to the membrane during cycled operation compared to the TiO_x support thus losing electronic contact. This issue should be addressed in the future by improving the catalyst synthesis to provide an enhanced inclusion of Ag in the Ti-suboxide structure.

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References

- [1] A.G. Olabi, M.A. Abdelkareem, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 158 (2022) 112111.
- [2] O. Pupo-Roncallo, D. Ingham, M. Pourkashanian, *Energy Reports*, 6 (2020) 242-248.
- [3] J.-N. Kang, Y.-M. Wei, L.-C. Liu, R. Han, B.-Y. Yu, J.-W. Wang, *Applied Energy*, 263 (2020) 114602.
- [4] J. Chi, H. Yu, *Chinese Journal of Catalysis*, 39 (2018) 390-394.
- [5] S. Wang, A. Lu, C.-J. Zhong, *Nano Convergence*, 8 (2021) 4.
- [6] L. Fan, Z. Tu, S.H. Chan, *Energy Reports*, 7 (2021) 8421-8446.
- [7] T. Chen, Y. Jin, H. Lv, A. Yang, M. Liu, B. Chen, Y. Xie, Q. Chen, *Transactions of Tianjin University*, 26 (2020) 208-217.
- [8] S. Shiva Kumar, V. Himabindu, *Materials Science for Energy Technologies*, 2 (2019) 442-454.
- [9] S. Siracusano, V. Baglio, N. Van Dijk, L. Merlo, A.S. Aricò, *Applied Energy*, 192 (2017) 477-489.
- [10] A.S. Aricò, S. Siracusano, N. Briguglio, V. Baglio, A. Di Blasi, V. Antonucci, *Journal of Applied Electrochemistry*, 43 (2013) 107-118.
- [11] C. Rakousky, U. Reimer, K. Wippermann, M. Carmo, W. Lueke, D. Stolten, *Journal of Power Sources*, 326 (2016) 120-128.
- [12] M.J. Burch, K.A. Lewinski, M.I. Buckett, S. Luopa, F. Sun, E.J. Olson, A.J. Steinbach, *Journal of Power Sources*, 500 (2021) 229978.
- [13] N. Li, S.S. Araya, X. Cui, S.K. Kær, *Journal of Power Sources*, 473 (2020) 228617.
- [14] S. Siracusano, S. Trocino, N. Briguglio, F. Pantò, A.S. Aricò, *Journal of Power Sources*, 468 (2020) 228390.
- [15] S. Kim, J.H. Han, J. Yuk, S. Kim, Y. Song, S. So, K.T. Lee, T.-H. Kim, *Journal of Power Sources*, 524 (2022) 231059.
- [16] M. Plevová, J. Hnát, K. Bouzek, *Journal of Power Sources*, 507 (2021) 230072.
- [17] E. Cossar, A.O. Barnett, F. Seland, R. Safari, G.A. Botton, E.A. Baranova, *Journal of Power Sources*, 514 (2021) 230563.
- [18] H. Liang, M. Xu, E. Asselin, *Journal of Power Sources*, 510 (2021) 230387.
- [19] S. Campagna Zignani, M.L. Faro, A. Carbone, C. Italiano, S. Trocino, G. Monforte, A.S. Aricò, *Electrochimica Acta*, 413 (2022) 140078.
- [20] Q. Feng, X.Z. Yuan, G. Liu, B. Wei, Z. Zhang, H. Li, H. Wang, *Journal of Power Sources*, 366 (2017) 33-55.
- [21] S.M. Saba, M. Müller, M. Robinius, D. Stolten, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 43 (2018) 1209-1223.
- [22] F. Pantò, S. Siracusano, N. Briguglio, A. Aricò, *Applied Energy*, 279 (2020).
- [23] C. Rozain, E. Mayousse, N. Guillet, P. Millet, *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental*, 182 (2016) 123-131.
- [24] C. Rozain, E. Mayousse, N. Guillet, P. Millet, *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental*, 182 (2016) 153-160.
- [25] D. Kulkarni, A. Huynh, P. Satjaritanun, M. O'Brien, S. Shimpalee, D. Parkinson, P. Shevchenko, F. DeCarlo, N. Danilovic, K.E. Ayers, C. Capuano, I.V. Zenyuk, *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental*, 308 (2022) 121213.
- [26] H. Yu, N. Danilovic, Y. Wang, W. Willis, A. Poozhikunnath, L. Bonville, C. Capuano, K. Ayers, R. Maric, *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental*, 239 (2018) 133-146.
- [27] Y. Zeng, X. Guo, Z. Shao, H. Yu, W. Song, Z. Wang, H. Zhang, B. Yi, *Journal of Power Sources*, 342 (2017) 947-955.
- [28] S. Siracusano, V. Baglio, S.A. Grigoriev, L. Merlo, V.N. Fateev, A.S. Aricò, *Journal of Power Sources*, 366 (2017) 105-114.
- [29] Y. Shi, K. Huang, L. Shen, C. Ding, Z. Lu, H. Tan, C. Guo, C. Yan, *Journal of Power Sources*, 549 (2022) 232130.
- [30] S. Siracusano, N. Van Dijk, E. Payne-Johnson, V. Baglio, A.S. Aricò, *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental*, 164 (2015) 488-495.

- [31] <https://pmm.unicore.com/en/prices/>
- [32] G. Carollo, A. Garbujo, F. Mauvy, A. Glisenti, *Energy & Fuels*, 34 (2020) 11438-11448.
- [33] Q. Pan, L. Wang, *Journal of Power Sources*, 485 (2021) 229335.
- [34] S. Dou, X. Wang, S. Wang, *Small Methods*, 3 (2019) 1800211.
- [35] A. Li, Y. Sun, T. Yao, H. Han, 24 (2018) 18334-18355.
- [36] Z. Xie, S. Yu, X. Ma, K. Li, L. Ding, W. Wang, D.A. Cullen, H.M. Meyer, H. Yu, J. Tong, Z. Wu, F.-Y. Zhang, *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental*, 313 (2022) 121458.
- [37] L. Shen, Y. Shi, T.O. Ogundipe, K. Huang, S. Cao, Z. Lu, Z. Wang, H. Tan, C. Yan, *Journal of Power Sources*, 538 (2022) 231557.
- [38] L. Li, P. Wang, Q. Shao, X. Huang, *Advanced Materials*, 33 (2021) 2004243.
- [39] J. Gao, H. Tao, B. Liu, *Advanced Materials*, 33 (2021) 2003786.
- [40] C. Di Giovanni, Á. Reyes-Carmona, A. Coursier, S. Nowak, J.M. Grenèche, H. Lecoq, L. Mouton, J. Rozière, D. Jones, J. Peron, M. Giraud, C. Tard, *ACS Catalysis*, 6 (2016) 2626-2631.
- [41] J. Ampurdanés, M. Chourashiya, A. Urakawa, *Catalysis Today*, 336 (2019) 161-168.
- [42] S. Siracusano, V. Baglio, C. D'Urso, V. Antonucci, A.S. Aricò, *Electrochimica Acta*, 54 (2009) 6292-6299.
- [43] X. Zhan, J. Zhang, M. Liu, J. Lu, Q. Zhang, F. Chen, *ACS Applied Energy Materials*, 2 (2019) 1685-1694.
- [44] M. Nagao, S. Misu, J. Hirayama, R. Otomo, Y. Kamiya, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*, 12 (2020) 2539-2547.
- [45] K.-L. Yan, J.-Q. Chi, J.-Y. Xie, B. Dong, Z.-Z. Liu, W.-K. Gao, J.-H. Lin, Y.-M. Chai, C.-G. Liu, *Renewable Energy*, 119 (2018) 54-61.
- [46] A. Jain, Z. Wang, J.K. Nørskov, *ACS Energy Letters*, 4 (2019) 1410-1411.
- [47] S. Siracusano, A. Stassi, E. Modica, V. Baglio, A.S. Aricò, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 38 (2013) 11600-11608.
- [48] A.S. Pushkarev, I.V. Pushkareva, D.G. Bessarabov, *Energy & Fuels*, 36 (2022) 6613-6625.
- [49] M. Möckl, M.F. Ernst, M. Kornherr, F. Allebrod, M. Bernt, J. Byrknes, C. Eickes, C. Gebauer, A. Moskovtseva, H.A. Gasteiger, *Journal of The Electrochemical Society*, 169 (2022) 064505.
- [50] S. Siracusano, S. Trocino, N. Briguglio, V. Baglio, A.S. Aricò, 11 (2018) 1368.
- [51] A. Naumkin, *Sci J Biomed Eng Biomed Sci.*, 2 (2018) 014 - 016.
- [52] J.F. Moulder, W.F. Stickle, P.E. Sobol, K.D. Bomben, *Handbook of X Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy*, Perkin-Elmer Corporation Physical Electronics Division, 1993.
- [53] A. Asha, S.L. Goyal, R. Dhankhar, R. Sharma, A. Sharma, *Indian Journal of Pure & Applied Physics (IJPAP)*, 60 (2022) 982 - 988.
- [54] D.S. Humphrey, C.L. Pang, Q. Chen, G. Thornton, *Nanotechnology*, 30 (2019) 025303.
- [55] N.V. Andreeva, D.A. Chigirev, A.S. Kunitsyn, A.A. Petrov, *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 443 (2018) 012003.
- [56] R. A. Bennett, *PhysChemComm*, 3 (2000) 9-14.
- [57] Q. Guo, I. Cocks, E.M. Williams, *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, 31 (1998) 2231-2235.
- [58] H. Nörenberg, G.A.D. Briggs, *Surface Science*, 402-404 (1998) 738-741.
- [59] M. Bernt, A. Hartig-Weiß, M.F. Tovini, H.A. El-Sayed, C. Schramm, J. Schröter, C. Gebauer, H.A. Gasteiger, *Chemie Ingenieur Technik*, 92 (2020) 31-39.
- [60] L. Wang, P. Lettenmeier, U. Golla-Schindler, P. Gazdzicki, N.A. Cañas, T. Morawietz, R. Hiesgen, S.S. Hosseiny, A.S. Gago, K.A. Friedrich, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 18 (2016) 4487-4495.